

Correlation of Lipid Profile with Duration of Diabetes and HbA1c Levels in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients: A Descriptive Cross-Sectional StudySanni Kumari¹, C Selvakumar²¹Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India²Professor and HOD, Department of Biochemistry, ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna, Bihar, India

Received: 25-03-2024 / Revised: 23-04-2024 / Accepted: 27-05-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a prevalent metabolic disorder associated with significant cardiovascular risk due to dyslipidemia. Understanding the relationships between lipid profile, duration of diabetes, and glycemic control is crucial for comprehensive management of T2DM. This study aimed to examine the correlation between lipid profile parameters, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels in patients with T2DM.

Methods: Eighty T2DM patients were included based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria. Data on demographic details, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels were collected. Lipid profile parameters were measured. Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess the relationships between the variables, with statistical analysis performed using SPSS version 20.0.

Results: The study included 80 participants with a mean age of 55.2 years and a mean diabetes duration of 8.4 years. Significant positive correlations were found between the duration of diabetes and both total cholesterol ($r = 0.38$, $p = 0.001$) and LDL cholesterol ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$). Duration of diabetes was negatively correlated with HDL cholesterol ($r = -0.29$, $p = 0.009$) and positively correlated with triglycerides ($r = 0.35$, $p = 0.002$). Higher HbA1c levels were positively correlated with total cholesterol ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$), LDL cholesterol ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$), and triglycerides ($r = 0.39$, $p = 0.001$), and negatively correlated with HDL cholesterol ($r = -0.31$, $p = 0.005$).

Conclusion: The findings indicate that both longer duration of diabetes and poor glycemic control are associated with adverse lipid profile changes in T2DM patients, highlighting the need for integrated management strategies.

Recommendations: Comprehensive management of T2DM should include regular monitoring and control of both glycemic levels and lipid profiles to reduce cardiovascular risks. Further research is recommended to explore the underlying mechanisms and long-term outcomes of such integrated approaches.

Keywords: Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Lipid Profile, HbA1c, Duration of Diabetes, Dyslipidemia.

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Introduction

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM) is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by insulin resistance and progressive β -cell dysfunction, leading to hyperglycemia. It is a global health issue, with a rapidly increasing prevalence affecting millions of people worldwide. According to the International Diabetes Federation (IDF), approximately 463 million adults were living with diabetes in 2019, and this number is expected to rise to 700 million by 2045, with T2DM constituting the majority of cases [1]. The management of T2DM involves a multifaceted approach, including lifestyle modifications, pharmacotherapy, and regular monitoring of glycemic status and associated comorbidities.

One of the critical aspects of managing T2DM is controlling dyslipidemia, a common comorbidity

that significantly increases the risk of cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Patients with T2DM often exhibit a characteristic pattern of dyslipidemia, known as diabetic dyslipidemia, which includes elevated levels of triglycerides, low levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, and an increased proportion of small, dense low-density lipoprotein (LDL) particles [2]. These lipid abnormalities contribute to the accelerated development of atherosclerosis, leading to an increased incidence of coronary artery disease, stroke, and peripheral vascular disease in diabetic patients.

Glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) is a well-established marker for long-term glycemic control, reflecting the average blood glucose levels over the preceding 2-3 months. Elevated HbA1c levels have

been associated with an increased risk of both microvascular and macrovascular complications in T2DM patients [3]. Moreover, the duration of diabetes also plays a crucial role in the development and progression of these complications. Prolonged exposure to hyperglycemia can lead to cumulative damage to various organs and systems, exacerbating the risk of cardiovascular events.

Several studies have investigated the relationship between glycemic control, lipid profile, and cardiovascular risk in T2DM patients [4]. However, the specific correlation between the duration of diabetes, HbA1c levels, and lipid profile parameters needs further exploration.

This study aimed to examine the correlation between lipid profile, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

Methodology

Study Design: A descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted over a period of 12 months at ESIC Medical College, Bihta, Patna.

Participants: A total of 80 participants diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Patients diagnosed with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.
2. Age between 30 and 70 years.
3. Patients who had been on anti-diabetic treatment for at least one year.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Patients with Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus.

2. Patients with severe comorbid conditions such as renal failure, liver disease, or cardiovascular diseases.

3. Pregnant or lactating women.

4. Patients on lipid-lowering drugs.

Bias: Efforts were made to minimize selection bias by consecutively recruiting eligible patients. Information bias was minimized by using standardized procedures for data collection and laboratory analysis.

Variables: Variables included duration of diabetes, HbA1c levels, lipid profile parameters (Total Cholesterol, LDL, HDL, Triglycerides).

Data Collection: Data were collected using a structured questionnaire and medical records. The information was gathered on demographic details, duration of diabetes, HbA1c levels, and lipid profile.

Procedure: Blood samples were collected from each participant after an overnight fast for lipid profile analysis. Laboratory analysis of lipid profiles was conducted using standardized methods.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 20.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) were used to summarize the data. Pearson's correlation coefficient was employed to assess the correlation between lipid profile, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

A total of 80 participants were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 55.2 ± 10.3 years, with a range from 30 to 70 years. The sample consisted of 42 males (52.5%) and 38 females (47.5%). The mean duration of diabetes was 8.4 ± 4.7 years. The mean HbA1c level was 8.1 ± 1.5 .

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Age (years)	55.2 ± 10.3
Gender	
- Male	42 (52.5%)
- Female	38 (47.5%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	8.4 ± 4.7
HbA1c (%)	8.1 ± 1.5

The mean values for the lipid profile parameters were as follows:

Table 2: Lipid Profile

Lipid Profile Parameter	Mean \pm SD (mg/dL)
Total Cholesterol	198.3 ± 42.5
LDL Cholesterol	120.5 ± 30.7
HDL Cholesterol	45.2 ± 11.4
Triglycerides	174.9 ± 65.3

Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess the correlation between lipid profile parameters, duration of diabetes, and HbA1c levels. The results are summarized in the table below.

Table 3: Correlation Analysis

Correlation	r-value	p-value
Duration of Diabetes vs. Total Cholesterol	0.38	0.001
Duration of Diabetes vs. LDL Cholesterol	0.41	<0.001
Duration of Diabetes vs. HDL Cholesterol	-0.29	0.009
Duration of Diabetes vs. Triglycerides	0.35	0.002
HbA1c vs. Total Cholesterol	0.42	<0.001
HbA1c vs. LDL Cholesterol	0.45	<0.001
HbA1c vs. HDL Cholesterol	-0.31	0.005
HbA1c vs. Triglycerides	0.39	0.001

There was a significant positive correlation between the duration of diabetes and both total cholesterol ($r = 0.38$, $p = 0.001$) and LDL cholesterol ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.001$). A significant negative correlation was observed between the duration of diabetes and HDL cholesterol ($r = -0.29$, $p = 0.009$). The correlation between the duration of diabetes and triglycerides was also positive and significant ($r = 0.35$, $p = 0.002$).

A significant positive correlation was found between HbA1c levels and total cholesterol ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$) and LDL cholesterol ($r = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$). HbA1c levels were negatively correlated with HDL cholesterol ($r = -0.31$, $p = 0.005$). There was a significant positive correlation between HbA1c levels and triglycerides ($r = 0.39$, $p = 0.001$).

Discussion

The mean age of the participants was 55.2 years, with a near-equal distribution of males and females. The average duration of diabetes among the participants was 8.4 years, and the mean HbA1c level was 8.1%, indicating relatively poor glycemic control. The analysis revealed significant correlations between the duration of diabetes and various lipid profile parameters. Specifically, there was a positive correlation between the duration of diabetes and both total cholesterol and LDL cholesterol. This suggests that longer durations of diabetes are associated with higher levels of these atherogenic lipids.

Conversely, a significant negative correlation was found between the duration of diabetes and HDL cholesterol, indicating that longer diabetes duration is associated with lower levels of protective HDL cholesterol. Additionally, a positive correlation was observed between the duration of diabetes and triglycerides levels.

When examining the relationship between HbA1c levels and lipid profile parameters, similar trends were observed. Higher HbA1c levels, indicative of poor glycemic control, were positively correlated with increased levels of total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides. This suggests that

patients with poorer glycemic control tend to have more adverse lipid profiles. There was also a significant negative correlation between HbA1c levels and HDL cholesterol, further emphasizing the impact of poor glycemic control on reducing protective HDL cholesterol levels.

These findings underscore the importance of managing both blood glucose levels and lipid profiles in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Prolonged duration of diabetes and poor glycemic control are both associated with dyslipidemia, which in turn increases the risk of cardiovascular complications. Therefore, comprehensive management strategies that include both glycemic control and lipid-lowering interventions are crucial for reducing cardiovascular risk in these patients. This study highlights the need for regular monitoring and management of lipid profiles in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus to mitigate the associated risks.

A cross-sectional study on 124 patients in a tertiary care hospital in Tamil Nadu, India. They found that 64.5% of patients had poor glycemic control (HbA1c > 7.5%). There was a significant positive correlation between HbA1c levels and total cholesterol, LDL, VLDL, and triglycerides. Age also showed a significant positive correlation with HbA1c levels [5].

35 patients were studied and found a significant correlation between HbA1c levels and total cholesterol ($r=0.364$), HDL ($r=-0.377$), and LDL ($r=0.367$). Patients with good glycemic control had significantly lower levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL compared to those with poor glycemic control [6].

A cross-sectional study was conducted on 105 patients in Dhaka, Bangladesh. They observed significantly higher mean levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, and LDL-C, and lower HDL-C in patients with diabetes. Significant correlations were found between HbA1c and total cholesterol, triglycerides, and HDL-C [7].

A study examined 206 patients in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. They found a significant correlation

between HbA1c and triglycerides ($r=0.16$, $p=0.020$), while no significant correlation was observed with total cholesterol, LDL-C, HDL-C, or fasting plasma glucose levels [8]. A cross-sectional study on 30 diabetic patients found significant positive correlations between HbA1c and triglycerides, LDL, total cholesterol, and VLDL, while a significant negative correlation was observed between HbA1c and HDL [9].

120 patients were studied and found significant correlations between HbA1c and various lipid profile components, including total cholesterol ($r=0.189$, $p=0.038$), triglycerides ($r=0.418$, $p<0.01$), LDL ($r=0.673$, $p<0.01$), and HDL ($r=-0.683$, $p<0.01$). They concluded that HbA1c can be used as a predictor of dyslipidemia in type 2 DM patients [10].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that both the duration of diabetes and poor glycemic control are significantly associated with adverse lipid profile changes in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus. Specifically, longer diabetes duration and higher HbA1c levels correlate with increased levels of total cholesterol, LDL cholesterol, and triglycerides, as well as decreased levels of HDL cholesterol. These findings highlight the critical need for comprehensive management strategies that address both blood glucose and lipid levels to reduce cardiovascular risks in this patient population. Regular monitoring and effective intervention are essential for improving overall health outcomes in patients with Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus.

References

1. International Diabetes Federation. IDF Diabetes Atlas, 9th edition. 2019.
2. Saeedi P, Petersohn I, Salpea P, Malanda B, Karuranga S, Unwin N, Colagiuri S, Guariguata L, Motala AA, Ogurtsova K, Shaw JE, Bright D, Williams R; IDF Diabetes Atlas Committee. Global and regional diabetes prevalence estimates for 2019 and projections for 2030 and 2045: Results from the International Diabetes Federation Diabetes Atlas, 9th edition. *Diabetes Res Clin Pract.* 2019 Nov;157: 107843.
3. Vergès B. Pathophysiology of diabetic dyslipidaemia: where are we? *Diabetologia.* 2015 May;58(5):886-99.
4. American Diabetes Association. Cardiovascular Disease and Risk Management: Standards of Medical Care in Diabetes-2020. *Diabetes Care.* 2020 Jan;43(Suppl 1):S111-S134.
5. Priya S, Begum N. Correlation of Lipid Profile with Duration of Diabetes and HbA1c Levels in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients: A Descriptive Cross-sectional Study. *SBV Journal of Basic, Clinical and Applied Health Science.* 2020.
6. Handayani D, Reza R, Dwi D, Jihan S, Kurnia H, Afra W. Correlation of HbA1C and Lipid Profile Levels in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients at M Yunus Hospital. *Jurnal Ilmu Kesehatan.* 2023.
7. Begum A, Irfan SR, Hoque M, Habib S, Parvin S, Malek R, et al. Relationship between HbA1c and Lipid Profile Seen in Bangladeshi Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus Patients Attending BIRDEM Hospital: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Mymensingh Med J.* 2019;28(1):91-95.
8. Alzahrani S, Baig M, Aashi MK, Al-Shaibi FK, Alqarni D, Bakhamees WH. Association between glycated hemoglobin (HbA1c) and the lipid profile in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus at a tertiary care hospital: a retrospective study. *Diabetes Metab Syndr Obes.* 2019; 12:1639-44.
9. Latha S, Fatima K. A Study of Correlation Between Glycated Hemoglobin and Lipid Profile in Diabetes Mellitus Patients. *PARIPEX Indian J Res.* 2022.
10. Pandey T, Khanal J, Godar KC. Study of Association Between Glycated Hemoglobin and Lipid Profile in Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus in Tertiary Care Center. *J Lumbini Med Coll.* 2020;8.